

Artificial Ground Truth Data Generation for Map Matching with Open Source Software

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Abstract: Map matching is a widely used technology for assigning tracks recorded by Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) to existing road networks. Due to the measurement uncertainty of GNSS positions, the biggest challenge is to map them accurately. To develop and verify suitable algorithms for map matching, ground truth, i.e., the traveled routes in the road network, is required as a reference. However, GNSS recorded tracks naturally lack the ground truth routes. Providing this data is time-consuming and costly in these cases, as it requires manual correction of the routes based on human memorization. This is not practical on a large scale, e.g., with floating car data (FCD). This is why there exist only a few isolated ground truth data sets that were created in this way for map matching. To close this gap, we introduce and evaluate in this work a new open source tool-chain for artificially generating large amounts of simulated ground truth routes for map matching. Based on these routes, we generate simulated FCD and we apply comparably authentic and parameterizable artificial GNSS noise with varying noise characteristics. The generated data allows to thoroughly evaluate and improve the performance of existing map matching algorithms and facilitates in future research the development of novel algorithms based on sufficiently large and diverse labeled data. In this work, we evaluate different scenarios of varying noise characteristics of our artificially generated ground truth data to compare the robustness, individual strengths, and weaknesses of existing open source map matching implementations. Our new approach of artificially generating ground truth data for map matching addresses the existing lack of sufficient available reference data for ongoing map matching research.

Keywords: artificial ground truth generation, traffic simulation, map matching, open source

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1 Introduction

The input to a map matching algorithm is a sequence of points, i.e., a track, acquired during the movement of a tracking device, e.g., a GNSS tracker, and an existing road network. Map matching algorithms then assign the points of the track to the edges of the existing road network graph and deduce a path through it containing all the assigned edge positions [4]. This results in a route, also called a “match”, that aligns exactly with the road network. In contrast, the input track does not lie on the road network due to GNSS measurement uncertainty.

Map matching is a method to resolve the discrepancies between recorded GNSS tracks and a given road network in a most plausible way, according to defined evaluation functions. These algorithms operate under the assumption that the given road network is complete and accurate [35, 36] and that only the given recorded tracks have significant discrepancies to the roads. Although road networks are not completely accurate by design, e.g., curves are usually modeled by short consecutive segments instead of splines, this is not an issue in map matching, as the goal is to find the most representative route within the road network rather than the true real-world positions of a track.

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A common use case for map matching is to match large scale FCD tracks, see Figure 1 for an example with artificial data. The routes that are shown in the left panel, which align exactly with the road network, do generally not exist in practice for real-world FCD. Only the noisy tracks, i.e., the FCD tracks recorded by GNSS trackers, that are shown in the middle panel exist in practice. For an example with real-world FCD that aligns with this Figure 1, also see the respective Figure 1 in [32]. Map matching the FCD tracks from the middle panel results in the routes that are shown in the right panel, which again align exactly with the road network and are close to the original routes shown in the left panel, which would ideally be the desired result. Thus, map matching results in an aggregation of all given FCD tracks onto existing road network segments.

Figure 1: Map Matching of artificial ground truth data. In the left panel is the simulated ground truth, in the middle panel are the artificially noised tracks from our approach, and in the right panel are the map matching results from our own open source software “Map Matching 2”.

Such aggregated matches enable the analysis of various traffic and movement pattern topics, such as road usage statistics or traffic flow analysis. These can provide valuable input for city and traffic planning use cases, such as road maintenance intervals, planning bypass constructions, or planning public transportation networks. In addition, not only large-scale FCD, but also individual, personal GNSS tracks, such as GPX records, can be individually matched as required for information purposes.

One of the main challenges in map matching is to find the routes that most accurately represent the given input tracks in the given road network, i.e., find the routes that would actually be driven in the road network. There are two major issues that complicate this process. First, due to data quality challenges [4], the discrepancy between the tracks and the road network can vary drastically. Second, there is usually no ground truth route in a given road network for a given input track available to train and evaluate algorithms against.

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Ground truth in the field of map matching “is a sequence of connected road segments of the traveled route on the map” [35] and “represents the correct path taken by the vehicle through the road network” [24]. Thus, ground truth in the context of map matching is not the actual “true geographical position” from which a GNSS point was measured but rather the “correct match” within the defined network.

The current lack of comprehensive ground truth data severely limits the ability to evaluate map matching algorithms, models, and metrics. Today, only a few ground truth data sets exist, as creating such data requires manually mapping GNSS records to predefined road networks, which is expensive. Other “reference” map matching data sets that were created by manually correcting map matching results are by definition not “ground truth” as the correct route in the road network remains unknown to the authors. These data sets are arguably subjective and sometimes also contain small oversight errors. Furthermore, evaluating map matching algorithms only on existing data sets bears the risk of introducing a general optimization bias. As such, the general availability of diverse and scalable ground truth data sets for map matching is an important aspect for ongoing map matching research.

Therefore, in this work we present an open source process for generating artificial ground truth map matching data sets by simulating routes on a given road network. These routes are then virtually driven by vehicle agents in a traffic micro-simulation software, with periodic emission of the exact virtual positions into sequence of points. On these tracks we then apply an artificial, parameterizable noise generation algorithm to simulate GNSS measurement uncertainty. The result of this process are artificial ground truth routes in a given road network and corresponding artificial GNSS tracks with synthetic noise applied.

This artificial generation approach differs from real-world cases where GNSS recordings are manually mapped to a road network after collection. In such cases, additional discrepancies arise because the recorded tracks and the defined road network usually come from slightly different true original geositions. In contrast, in our artificial process, the ground truth route is created before the track positions are emitted, and both originate from the same geositions. Thus, there exist no discrepancies between the ground truth route and the track positions before artificial noise is added to the track, which eliminates a source of error for the training and evaluation of map matching algorithms that real-world data usually contains.

Simulating artificial GNSS noise comes with some challenges. Real-world GNSS noise has various sources of disturbance, such as weather phenomena or satellite opacity, which cannot be accurately represented in a virtual process to date. However, current map matching models are not designed to accurately resolve real-world GNSS disturbances, as they rely on simplified statistical methods that evaluate, for example, distances or angles between points. Thus, we hypothesize that generating artificial noise with similar statistical distributions as real-world GNSS noise is sufficient for producing meaningful ground truth data for map matching research.

As long as there is no technology for measuring real-world geositions with absolute precision under any circumstances, or a technology that is able to completely resolve the measurement uncertainty of GNSS measurements, there will always be some discrepancies between recorded GNSS geositions and already defined road networks, which generally also rely on recorded GNSS geositions. This ongoing discrepancy is addressed with map matching and as such, robust and accurate map matching solutions remain needed.

1.1 Literature and State of the Art

Our work is based on various existing research in the fields of GNSS (i.e., GPS error distribution), traffic simulation (i.e., the open source tool SUMO), and map matching (i.e., data sets, models and algorithms, benchmarking, and our own open source implementation).

Previous approaches to provide map matching ground truth routes hand-matched [16, 24] self-recorded GNSS tracks. Currently, there exist only two tracks with one ground truth route each, one from [16] and one from [24]. There has also been work on hand-correcting [15, 23, 32] the results of an initial map matching of tracks with the ground truth routes being unknown to the authors. However, this only lead to an additional 100 [15], 10 [23], and 264 [32] tracks and some of the “reference” routes, i.e., not “ground truth” routes, contain small errors due to human oversight.

In our previous work [32] we described, evaluated, and compared the three real-world GNSS map matching data sets from [15, 16, 24] and our own fourth real-world data set with existing open source map matching tools against our own map matching implementation “Map Matching 2” (<https://github.com/iisys-hof/map-matching-2>) [32] in a detailed benchmark. Among the other open source map matching solutions were, e.g., Barefoot (<https://github.com/bmwcarit/barefoot>) [19], Fast map matching (<https://github.com/cyang-kth/fmm>) (FMM) [33], Map Matching based on GraphHopper (<https://github.com/graphhopper/graphhopper#mapmatching>), Open Source Routing Machine (<https://github.com/Project-OSRM/osrm-backend>) (OSRM) [20], and Valhalla (<https://github.com/valhalla/valhalla>). Sub-section 1.3 and Table 1 in our previous work [32] provide more details on the technologies and models of these tools, which we also benchmark in this work.

All third-party tools rely on the Hidden Markov Model (HMM) as a stochastic method for evaluating alternate paths between possible matching solutions for finding an optimal solution concerning the defined models and metrics, except for FMM, which also implements ST-Match [18], a simpler stochastic model. Our own “Map Matching 2” tool primarily relies on a more robust Markov Decision Process (MDP) [32], but we also implemented the traditional HMM for direct comparison purposes. There are several review works about the history and current state of research about map matching [4, 6, 10, 11, 25]. As of today, stochastic methods are the most accurate models. However, the general accuracy still needs to improve, which, in our opinion, mainly originates from the challenging noise characteristics of GNSS noise in general.

The results from the benchmark in our previous work [32] on the real-world GNSS map matching data sets showed that our solution outperforms the other solutions in terms of accuracy and mostly also in terms of computational resources, especially when put in relation with the achieved accuracy. Due to some recent software updates of our own “Map Matching 2” solution, our open source code repository now contains examples with newer accuracy and computational resource benchmark results in the “data” folder for all mentioned real-world GNSS data sets. The achieved accuracy currently is 98.73 % [15], 99.80 % [16], 98.59 % [23] (with two large data errors manually corrected, see repository explanation), 99.89 % [24], and 99.58 % [32].

Concerning GNSS, there exist various implementations, e.g., Global Positioning System (GPS) (<https://www.gps.gov/>), Galileo (<https://www.gsa.europa.eu/>), GLONASS (<https://www.glonass-iac.ru/en/>), or Beidou (<http://en.beidou.gov.cn/>). However, in this work we focus

on GPS, because currently existing map matching data sets, as well as OpenStreetMap (OSM), all use the GPS spatial reference system WGS-84. Furthermore, SUMO also emits GPS coordinates as virtual FCD, and real-world FCD also generally contains GPS coordinates. Therefore, GPS is currently the most common and compatible choice.

The most relevant topic of GPS for this work is the GPS error distribution. Due to atmospheric disturbances [13] and signal reflections [22], GPS is said to have an accuracy range of at least several meters. In [30] the error range with smartphones in an open space was measured to be within 4.9 m. In [12] the ≈ 5 m range of smartphone GPS accuracy in an open space is confirmed, and it is shown that the error also depends on the GPS site, i.e., location on the globe. Furthermore, it is shown that near buildings the error is $\approx 3 - 4$ times higher, up to ≈ 15 m – 20 m, which is especially relevant for FCD, i.e., driving in cities while navigating with smartphones. When satellite opacity [9] happens, i.e., when a GPS receiver loses contact with enough GPS satellites at a time for locating its position, for example, because of buildings, hills, bridges, or tunnels, large outliers can occur. These outliers are outside the regular noise distribution and can reach several hundreds of meters in practice. For example, the map matching data set from Newson and Krumm [24] contains such an outlier with > 100 m.

GPS error is spatially and temporally autocorrelated, as was extensively researched by analyzing stationary GNSS records [8, 9, 26, 27, 29]. In [8] the authors show that the GNSS distance error mostly follows a Rayleigh distribution. A Rayleigh distribution is a probability distribution for non-negative Gaussian distributed values. The GNSS longitude and latitude measurements mostly follow a Gaussian distribution, which is also shown in [9], which makes the GNSS distance error as the “geometric sum of latitude and longitude errors” [9] similar to a Rayleigh distribution [9]. In [8] the authors also state that using an error distribution that does not account autocorrelation leads to a different kind of error, as “the data would fluctuate randomly without the autocorrelation phenomena” [8]. This would happen, e.g., with using a Gaussian distribution for simulating GNSS error.

Autocorrelation means that succeeding measurements with close timestamps generally have similar shifts on the axes within the accuracy means. GNSS measurements are time-dependent on previous values, but over time they become less dependent. The reasons for this are that within close timestamps, the satellite positions, atmospheric disturbances, and earth rotation are similar and they diverge the more time goes by. In [9] the authors show a GNSS error autocorrelation function, a GNSS error over time, and moving average smoothing of the error over time, to give an impression of the autocorrelation of GNSS measurements. The authors also show an example of how the distance error significantly raises when satellite opacity happens. Such outliers lie far outside the original error distribution and autocorrelation. In [26] the spatial and temporal autocorrelation is also confirmed. Moreover it is shown that GPS distance errors overestimate actual distances, i.e., a GPS track recorded at a static position is always longer than the static recording device has actually moved.

In [27] the authors simulate GPS error with an Autoregressive (AR) model and they validate their synthetic GPS data with real-world collected data to show that autocorrelated models are able to simulate the noise characteristics of real-world GPS data. In [29] the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process with the Euler-Maruyama method is applied for simulating GPS noise. In the same work, also the simple Gaussian distribution, the AR model, the Moving Average (MA) model, and the Autoregressive Moving Average Model (ARMA) are evaluated. The au-

thors explain that while the AR, MA, and ARMA models are autocorrelated, only the OU model is additionally mean-reverting, which means that the noise generated over time not only depends on its previous values but simultaneously returns to a defined value, for example, zero, with the attraction being greater the further away the current error is from the defined value. The authors in [29] also show in their Figure 6 that OU generated noise is similarly autocorrelated as real GPS noise, in their case most closely comparable up to two hours. Since the OU process is also based on a Gaussian process for the random value generation, the OU process gives a similar GNSS error distribution as real GPS error over time.

On the topic of traffic simulation, there are various implementations that have been proven to model traffic with sufficient accuracy [3, 21, 28]. Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO) [14] is an open source micro traffic simulation tool that supports OSM road networks and FCD output for generating routes that are virtually driven while simultaneously emitting GPS coordinates as GPS tracks. Traffic can be generated in various ways, for example, randomly, with origin-destination (OD) matrices, based on road counting data, turn probabilities, or based on activities, e.g., based on population distribution with the SAGA tool-chain [5].

There are a few previous works that generate map matching ground truth data based on a traffic simulation. However, the complete processes are not openly available. In [7] traffic is simulated based on SUMO, and the onboard “traceExporter.py” tool is used for applying artificial noise based on a simple Gaussian distribution. As such, the artificial error is not autocorrelated. The authors use a sampling interval of 30 s with a Gaussian distribution standard deviation σ of 5 m. Using a low sampling interval helps in mitigating the effects of autocorrelation, as samples further apart are less autocorrelated, especially with moving vehicles in cities. In [17] traffic is also simulated based on SUMO, and the open source tool GNSS-INS-SIM (<https://github.com/Aceinna/gnss-ins-sim>) is used for generating artificial noise, again, based on a simple Gaussian distribution. They use sampling intervals of 1 s, 5 s, and 10 s with respective Gaussian distribution standard deviation σ of 5 m, 10 m, and 20 m. Since the used noise distributions are not autocorrelated in these works, only low noise can be used with high sampling intervals, or else the track shape degrades significantly when high uncorrelated normal noise is applied on a high sampling interval.

1.2 Approach

To address the ongoing lack of available map matching ground truth data, we present in this work an open process based on an open source software for generating diverse artificial map matching ground truth data sets on OSM road network extracts. We use SUMO for simulating the artificial ground truth routes and for extracting the FCD positions, initially without error. We then apply a new open source implementation for adding artificial autocorrelated GNSS noise based on the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process to the FCD. This tool also implements the simple Gaussian distribution and the ARMA model for comparison purposes. We also implement parameterizable moving average smoothing on the generated noise to account for excessive jittering of the underlying Gaussian random values. Additionally, our tool allows for applying simple random outliers with parameterizable distribution closeness along the tracks for simulating potential satellite opacity. We also deploy additional settings and tools for analyzing the generated noise distributions and the track characteristics. We evaluate the generated synthetic GNSS noise distributions against real-world GPS recordings to show that our process is able to achieve authentic GNSS noise results within certain limitations. Finally, we compare multiple diverse artificial generated map matching ground truth

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data sets with different open source map matching tools and our own implementation to reveal different strengths and weaknesses of all tools depending on the input track data noise characteristics.

Figure 2: Technology roadmap for our artificial ground truth generation open source tool-chain. The rectangle shapes show processes and tools, the trapezium shapes show artifacts, the cylinders show the input and output data. The processes and tools in the “SUMO” frame are provided by SUMO, the tools in the “New” frame below are newly provided from us. The “ground-truth.csv” and “points.csv” files are the essential results of our pipeline that are further matched and evaluated. The “map-matching” and “comparison” processes are existing open source algorithms. The rest are intermediate files.

2 Method

In Figure 2 we present the step-by-step process of how we generate artificial map matching ground truth data with our new approach. First, the OSM road network is converted into the SUMO format with “netconvert”. We use some additional parameters for reducing the internal lane and junction area sizes so that the emitted FCD stays close to the original geositions from OSM. Next, we generate movements with “randomTrips.py” from the SUMO package. Instead of random movements, more sophisticated trip generation algorithms may be used, but random movements can be generated for any region or city without additional knowledge. The resulting movements are then simulated with the “sumo” command, i.e., virtual vehicles drive the generated routes, and FCD is emitted every second. The raw FCD XML output then is converted into the intermediate GPSDAT format with the SUMO “traceExporter.py” utility.

We continue our workflow with converting the GPSDAT format into a FCD CSV file with Well-Known-Text (WKT) point representation, as this facilitates further processing in our pipeline. We also export the ground truth routes from the SUMO network and the generated routes

XML file, i.e., the exact OSM edges are exported into WKT lines. Finally, we apply our artificial noise generation on the input FCD tracks, which results in the noisy points CSV file. This file is then matched with map matching, and the results are compared with the extracted ground truth routes. In this way, we are able to measure the accuracy of a map matching algorithm depending on the defined artificial noise characteristics on the FCD tracks.

2.2 Artificial GNSS noise

One of the key aspects of this work is the artificial noise generation process. With our “apply_error.py” tool, simple Gaussian, ARMA, or OU distributed noise can be generated. In addition, simple outliers can be added with a closeness parameter that describes how likely outliers lie directly next to each other, for simulating satellite opacity. Outliers are sampled from a Gaussian distribution, as they do not follow the autocorrelation of regular GNSS noise.

The Gaussian (normal) distribution is uncorrelated and, although frequently used in previous research, does not correctly represent GNSS error over time:

$$X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$$

with μ := zero (mean); σ := error (standard deviation);

The autoregressive moving-average (ARMA) process is autocorrelated but contains no term for mean-reversion, which means that it offsets further from the zero-mean the longer it runs. The white noise term is sampled from a simple Gaussian distribution:

$$X_t = \varepsilon_t + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \varepsilon_{t-i}$$

with φ_i := autoregressive terms; θ_i := moving-average terms; ε_t := white noise; p := autoregressive order; q := moving-average order;

Therefore, the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process with Euler-Maruyama method contains a mean-reversion term, so that it stays within close bounds of the zero-mean even over a long time, which comes closer to real GNSS noise autocorrelation. The Wiener process term is also sampled from a simple Gaussian distribution:

$$X_t = X_{t-1} + \theta(\mu - X_{t-1})\Delta t + \sigma W_{t-1} \sqrt{\Delta t}$$

with θ := rate of mean reversion; μ := long-term mean; σ := volatility; W := Wiener process (standard Brownian motion); Δt := time step size;

In addition to the noise processes, we apply a moving average smoothing on the sampled noise. For high-sampled noise, the autocorrelated processes still jitter more than regular GNSS noise, which comes from the underlying Gaussian distribution randomness. With low sampling intervals, the smoothing can gradually be disabled completely, as the autocorrelation is lower, the longer the time distance between two samples is.

2.2 Noise comparison

In Figure 3 we show, for an example track, an exaggerated noise distribution of simple Gaussian noise, compared with exaggerated ARMA and OU noise. The noise generation seed is the same in all variants. It can be seen that the Gaussian noise does not yield practi-

cal results for high-sampled tracks due to the missing autocorrelation. The ARMA process yields much more authentic results, but it diverges from the zero-mean as time passes, which leads to larger differences between the input and the output track, especially at the end of the tack. The OU process is autocorrelated and also mean-reverting, and thus is the only noise process in comparison, which is suitable for long-time high-sampling noise generation. We can see that compared to ARMA, it slowly reverts towards the zero-mean as time passes. We can also see how the moving average smoothing further reduces the jittering of the noise that comes from the underlying Gaussian process.

Figure 3: Noise comparison of normal (Gaussian), autoregressive moving-average (ARMA), and Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) noise on an example track from the SUMO simulation. Also is shown the noise after moving average smoothing with a window size of 10. In addition, the autocorrelation functions (ACF) are shown.

2.3 Hypertuning and Noise characteristics validation

We made two experiments for validating the artificially generated GNSS noise against real-world GNSS data. In the first experiment, we compare the GNSS noise distributions from a training of artificially generated data against real GNSS data, i.e., FCD, by learning the error, outlier distribution, and outlier error parameters from our artificial noise generation process. These parameters were selected because the real-world GNSS data contains an unknown error distribution and unknown outliers. We first matched the original FCD with our “Map Matching 2” application and exported the distances of all track GNSS points to their final road positions, called “target distances”. Then we used the Python library Optuna [1] and trained

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the artificial error generation parameters until the distances from the artificial data, called “hypertuning distances”, were similar to the target distances. We also evaluated and tuned the outlier occurrence and outlier distance distribution. For the time delta, we used 5 s to reflect the median time delta of 5 s from the real-world target FCD data. In Figure 4, we can see that both error distance distributions are similar to a Rayleigh distribution and also similar to each other after hypertuning. This shows that our artificial noise generation process can learn the parameters from real-world GNSS data and it can generate artificial noise that has comparable distance error distributions as real-world GNSS data. In addition, we show an exemplary excerpt from the real-world target FCD and the artificially generated FCD after hypertuning. The track and the outlier distance error distributions around the roads are of a similar magnitude, although the artificial data of course consists of different routes and different concrete outliers than the real-world FCD. The real-world FCD data has $\approx 3.34\%$ of outliers and the artificial FCD after hypertuning has $\approx 3.38\%$ of generated outliers, both analyzed with Tukey's fences with $k = 3$ on the distances.

Figure 4: Hypertuning results of the GNSS error parameter estimation on real-world FCD. The left panel shows the target and hypertuned distance error distributions. The center panel shows the distance distribution and outliers of the real-world target FCD on a map. The right panel shows the distance distribution and outliers of the artificially noised FCD with the hypertuned parameters on a map.

Figure 5: Hypertuning results of the GNSS error parameter estimation on a real-world stationary GNSS record of one hour. The left panel shows the real-world and the artificial GNSS track with their centroid. Both start in the north, go to the south, and lie in a similar region close to each other. The middle panel shows the coordinates in comparison. We can see that our artificial coordinates overall fit to the real curves, with some unrepresented discrepancies in smaller parts. Moreover, the real values have a very fine jittering that our moving average smoothed curves have not. The autocorrelation functions (ACF) have similar dimensions, although the longitude could not be represented as good as the latitude in this example.

In a second experiment, we recorded GNSS points with a smartphone in a static position at a window in a building for roughly one hour. We anonymized the data by translating it to the (0, 0) coordinate and then we hypertuned the artificial process on a simulated track that was created from the centroid of the recorded GNSS track as “assumed real position”. In this experiment, the error, the OU reversion speed, the moving average smoothing, and the random seed parameters were hypertuned. The parameters were chosen because the real GNSS points this time not only have an unknown error distribution but, due to being static, also a very long run-time, which needs for a finer autocorrelation and smoothing factor tuning. Moreover, we chose between 100 distinct random seed parameters to find one that represents the actual curve of the recorded track better than other seeds. In practice, the seed has no impact on the distributions on average over many random values, but for comparing a specific track shape, it helps to select a favorable seed that generates the noise in a similar direction. Figure 5 shows that we can generate an artificial track that has a somewhat resembling track shape within similar bounds as the original real-world GNSS record. Although we could not represent the start of the curve as good as the remainder, the dimensions and the autocorrelations, especially for the latitudes, show that our process can generate fairly authentic GNSS noise even for longer durations.

We can see that our artificial noise generation has some limitations, for example, real GNSS noise contains a very fine jittering that we cannot accurately represent yet. Without moving average smoothing, the artificial jittering is too high, as shown in Figure 4. With moving average smoothing, the jittering is too small in direct comparison. With additional work, it should be possible to re-apply a fine noise again after smoothing. However, we believe that this missing fine jittering is not an impactful issue, since the jittering is very fine in comparison to the actual distance error.

Although the artificially generated GNSS noise is only a model of real-world GNSS noise, we hypothesize that this is sufficient for an evaluation, because map matching metrics are very simplified in contrast to real-world GNSS error dynamics and they also can contain terms, such as direction changes of the computed road network routes, see Figure 11 in [32], that are not even present in the GNSS tracks. As such, the artificial GNSS error does not need to be perfectly accurate, as map matching algorithms are not designed to accurately resolve GNSS errors.

3 Experiments

For analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of existing open source map matching tools, we execute a benchmark on one sample of 1000 simulated SUMO tracks on an OSM road network extract from the city of Hof, Bavaria, Germany. For generating the artificial noise, we used the hypertuned parameters as well as custom-chosen settings for testing a variety of more authentic and more extreme noise characteristics with and without simple outliers.

One limitation of our benchmark is that different map matching tools process the road network data differently. For example, some tools might remove roads that others keep, and some tools handle turn restrictions, while others ignore them. This naturally impacts the map matching results even when the original road network input is the same for all tools. However, to reflect practical real-world scenarios, in which this limitation similarly exists between the different tools, we explicitly allow and keep this situation in our experiments.

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Table 1: Parameter definitions for our benchmark experiments. We define as B the baseline experiments without error applied, as H5 the hypertuned scenario with 5 s sampling interval, as E the typical error scenarios with L = low, M = mid, and H = high error, as O the outlier scenarios, and as S the sparse scenarios with 10 s to 30 s between two points. We define the error standard deviation σ , the smoothing window size w , the outlier probability p , the outlier standard deviation error σ , the time step δ , and the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process Δt . All other parameters were the default parameters from the “apply_error.py” tool.

	H5	B	EL	EM	EH	OL	OM	OH	B10	B20	B30	S10	S20	S30
error σ	0.8	0	1	2	3	1	2	3	0	0	0	1	2	3
smooth w	2	1	10	20	30	10	20	30	1	1	1	1	1	1
outlier p	0.022					0.01	0.02	0.03						
outlier σ	43.81					30	40	50						
time δ	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	20	30	10	20	30
OU Δt	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	20	30	10	20	30

We define multiple experiment scenarios according to Table 1. The baseline scenarios are run without errors, i.e., the baseline is matching the unmodified simulated FCD without any noise added to compare how well a tool matches the FCD without noise already. We hypothesize that a tool cannot surpass the baseline with the same sampling interval after noise has been added to the FCD.

Table 2: Hypertuned scenario detailed results from our benchmark. Accuracy is the “weighted mean correct fraction”, Time is in elapsed seconds, CPU resources are the sum of user and sys CPU seconds, MEM is the maximum resident set size in MiB. The Time, CPU, and MEM resources are taken from the best out of ten runs to reduce the impact of software running simultaneously.

Software	Version	Language	Accuracy	Time	CPU	MEM
Map Matching 2	1.0.5	C++	0.9953	1.41	84.76	1429
Barefoot	2021-08-18	Java	0.9737	34.30	4348.23	22,347
OSRM	5.27.1	C++	0.8955	6.58	7.08	46
GraphHopper	10	Java	0.8204	8.29	681.78	1860
Valhalla	3.5.1	C++	0.7693	8.34	64.53	7426
FMM (HMM)	2024-04-22	C++	0.7416	18.95	31.27	1538
FMM (STMatch)	2024-04-22	C++	0.5256	0.69	24.21	68

$$a = \frac{c}{\max(g, m)}$$

with c := length of correct match parts; g := length of ground truth; m := length of match

The accuracy metric, i.e., correct fraction, is computed after the accuracy equation above, as was already suggested in [2, 31, 34] and in our previous work [32]. There, we computed the “mean correct fraction” as the average of all individual accuracies, without taking the match and ground truth lengths into account. In this work we compute the “weighted mean correct fraction” by computing the accuracy over the sum of all correct matched parts over the length of all matches, respective ground truth routes. This means that the accuracy metric in this work is weighted after track length, so that small tracks with low accuracy don’t impact the

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overall accuracy metric as much as it would be the case in the unweighted variant. As such, the accuracy results are not directly comparable with the results from our previous work.

In Table 2 we have the results from the hypertuned noise tracks with additional details about CPU and memory resource consumption. The CPU seconds are the time in seconds the application would need when only using one thread on one CPU core. If both values are close to each other, it means that the application did not scale well with multithreading. A higher difference fraction means that the individual CPU cores were used more in parallel. This table also shows the used software versions and programming languages. We can see that our “Map Matching 2” implementation has the highest accuracy, a comparably good resource consumption, and it is the second fastest solution. Barefoot is closely following, but uses much more CPU and memory resources. OSRM uses the least resources, but also has a much lower accuracy. GraphHopper again needs more CPU resources and is also less accurate. Valhalla uses the second most memory and is only slightly more accurate than FMM, which comes in last. In particular, the simpler STMatch model does not give good accuracy, although it does not use many resources either.

Table 3: Experiment results from our benchmark. The values are the accuracy metric “weighted mean correct fraction” between 0.0 and 1.0 with 0.0 having 0 % accuracy and 1.0 having 100 % accuracy.

	Map Matching 2	Barefoot	OSRM	GraphHopper	Valhalla	FMM (HMM)	FMM (STMatch)
H5	0.9953	0.9737	0.8955	0.8204	0.7693	0.7416	0.5256
B	0.9968	0.9960	0.8753	0.9860	0.9321	0.9955	0.5678
EL	0.9960	0.9950	0.7404	0.6407	0.9296	0.5644	0.2517
EM	0.9931	0.9779	0.2843	0.2795	0.9159	0.3704	0.1591
EH	0.9823	0.9275	0.1632	0.2024	0.8491	0.2842	0.1230
OL	0.9957	0.9706	0.6099	0.4996	0.5964	0.4747	0.2086
OM	0.9843	0.9018	0.1677	0.2239	0.2601	0.2955	0.1163
OH	0.9525	0.8006	0.0805	0.1618	0.1495	0.2122	0.0812
B10	0.9951	0.9964	0.9529	0.9857	0.9856	0.9908	0.9520
B20	0.9904	0.9933	0.9424	0.9832	0.9870	0.9802	0.9803
B30	0.9830	0.9883	0.9493	0.9804	0.9817	0.9655	0.9647
S10	0.9936	0.9937	0.9265	0.8798	0.9826	0.8251	0.6540
S20	0.9839	0.9508	0.6881	0.7736	0.9808	0.6861	0.5691
S30	0.9603	0.8773	0.4795	0.7300	0.9220	0.6220	0.5355

In Table 3 we can see the accuracy metrics of all evaluated track sets in comparison with all tools. We can see that our own “Map Matching 2” implementation achieves high accuracy in all situations, even with large outliers (OH) where most other tools drastically degrade in accuracy. Barefoot often stays close and also handles noise comparably well, and it is the only other tool that can tolerate outliers up to some extent. In some of the sparse scenarios, it

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even has slightly higher accuracy than our solution, but it is less accurate than our solution in dense scenarios with 1 s sampling interval and when the error is higher. OSRM and Graph-Hopper both benefit from sparse-sampled tracks and degrade quickly with higher error and especially with outliers applied. Valhalla is not so sensitive to higher error and has good accuracy in high and especially in low-sampling situations (S10, S20), but it degrades a lot with outliers. FMM only achieves some accuracy with sparse and low error, especially with its simpler STMatch model. Already in the baseline scenario with 1 s sampling interval, the STMatch model of FMM has an exceptionally low accuracy, although no noise has been applied yet. Overall, our own implementation is the most robust in comparison and can be recommended for any tracks with any noise characteristics. We also have discovered several individual strengths and weaknesses of the other open source map matching tools, depending on the noise and sampling interval characteristics of the GNSS tracks.

4 Discussion

In this work, we have presented a new approach for generating artificial ground truth map matching data sets with open source software based on traffic simulation with artificial auto-correlated noise generation. We have shown that our new approach can generate authentic synthetic noise within certain limitations and also intentional extreme noise for worst case analysis. We have also shown how this process can be used to reveal hidden strengths and weaknesses of map matching algorithms in practice.

Our artificial noise still has some limitations. Currently, we only generate simple outliers by moving individual points, selected by a closeness probability parameter, to a random position from a Gaussian distribution that is independent of the OU process. Additional analysis of real-world outliers is required to further improve the authenticity of the artificial outliers and to make them more diverse.

Furthermore, the application of traffic micro-simulation may limit the size of the road networks that can be used efficiently. However, the amount of GNSS tracks that can be generated by our approach, and that we have artificially generated in this work, already exceeds all existing map matching data sets combined. In this way, our new approach of artificially generating map matching ground truth data facilitates further improvements in map matching research and development.

Data and codes availability

Our open source tools and benchmark are available under AGPL 3.0 (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html>) at FigShare (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27952545>).

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